

Proving the Riemann Hypothesis Using QFT And Varying Lorentz Manifolds

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Abstract:

The following is a prove that primes numbers are forming a non-abelian group of the form $2(N+1/2)$ with $1/2$ as generator. The paper is divided to three parts. The first revolving on deriving fermions and their anti-commutation relation from Manifolds. Second part uses the anti-commutation fermions on the primes problem. The third and final part revolves around using functors to reach the desired result and finalize the proof. If the following proof to be accepted, it is an elegant and beautiful result that will lead to important advancements in our understanding. The methodology contains functors, EL framework (Cal. of variations), group theory and Quantum field theory. No Non Trivial zeros were calculated by hand, which makes the proof very elegant compared to what has been done in that regard.

Introduction

Define a Lorentz manifold: Define a Lorentz manifold, which is the connected manifold with (3,1) signature:

$$s = (M, g)$$

Invoke it to be stationary by Euler Lagrange operator, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$:

$$\mathcal{L} = (s, s', t)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} - \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} = 0$$

Develop the last equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

If the Lorenz manifold to be stationary and no data is attainable from the first three terms, we can require the manifold to those two conditions:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

If these two are hold to be true, we have areas of extremum curvature on the manifold and negative time invariant acceleration. The demand of extrunum curvature to stay as they are overtime means the acceleration cannot affect them – if so, directed away from them. This in agreement with what we speculate as "dark energy".

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish. Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we can derive the existence of fermions, i.e. showing that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Suppose four distinct elements:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Than the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need even amounts of equal elements of pluses and minuses. The amount must be even and summed as zero, ensuring stationary Lorentz manifold. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

Or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will exclude this result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish to zero. As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$0: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(0)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps.

So:

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

The first two combinations are by the natural maps and one used them to build the other combinations. Overall, there are eight such combinations and additional one arrow combination, which yield (333). Here is how one built it, starting from those two natural maps. (Arrows to variations, colors to pairings):

Now that we have a series of $2N$ elements, varying to one another and forming threefold combinations, which we require to vanish at end, we can set the stage for a proof of primes:

Define: P^m as the set of $\{2, 3\}$ as "minimal primes"

In addition, all the other primes to be in a set of P_h as meant "prime higher".

Define $P_h = \{2n + 1\}$ not divisible by P^m as "prime higher" set – $2n$ taken as amount of Lorentz manifold arbitrary variations.

as an odd amount of variations not divisible by minimal primes $\{2n + 1\}$

$$P_t = P_h + P^m; \text{ to be the set of all primes}$$

.Define a functor V on P_h :

$$V: \text{set} \rightarrow \text{ring}$$

Analyze any multiplication or addition combination of P_h on the ring. Let the ring

Exist on a Lorentz manifold, a topological space.

Multiplication:

Define T to be a number aspiring infinity: $T \rightarrow \infty$

Multiply an even or odd series aspiring infinity of distinct higher primes to obtain:

$$[(2n_1 + 1)(2n_2 + 1)(2n_3 + 1) \dots (2n + 1)] =$$

$$2 \left[T ((n_1 n_2 \dots)) + (n_1 + n_2 + n_3 \dots) + \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$= 2([T ((n_1 n_2 \dots)) + N(s) + 1/2]) \quad (11)$$

$$N(s) = (n_1 + n_2 + n_3 \dots) = 0. \quad (12)$$

As sums of even amounts of arbitrary variations vanish. Since all the elements are two multiples, they all vanish. Final form:

$$2([T (n_1 n_2 \dots)] + 1/2) \quad (13)$$

Addition

Add any infinite even series of distinct higher primes to obtain

$$(2n_1 + 1) + (2n_2 + 1) + (2n_3 + 1) \dots = [2(n_1 + n_2 \dots) + \text{even}] =$$

$$[2(n_1 + n_2 \dots)] \quad (14)$$

$$\text{as even} = 0.$$

Prime cannot form, as even amount of variations vanish exactly to zero. That is the reason the paper begins with deriving fermions, their anti-commutation relation. Even amount of distinct higher primes added will never form a prime.

Add any infinite odd series of distinct higher primes to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2n_1 + 1) + (2n_2 + 1) + (2n_3 + 1) \dots &= \\
 [2(n_1 + n_2 \dots) + \text{odd}] &= \\
 [2(n_1 + n_2 \dots) + (\text{even} + 1)] & \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

However, even amounts of arbitrary variations vanish:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{even} &= 0 \\
 [2(n_1 + n_2 \dots) + 1] &\text{ or:} \\
 2[n_1 + n_2 \dots + 1/2] & \quad (16)
 \end{aligned}$$

Category transformations

Define a functor on "Primes higher" ring

$$G: \text{ring} \rightarrow \text{group}$$

All "primes higher" are forming a closed non-abelian group with 1/2 as generator. The condition to group forming is to have an odd amount of primes under addition and eliminating even amounts of arbitrary variations taken as an axiom.

Define additional functor

$$G': \text{group} \rightarrow \text{set}$$

Add the sets:

$$P_h + P^m = P_t ;$$

Define a functor on P_t :

$$G'': \text{set} \rightarrow \text{group}$$

All primes are forming a non-abelian group of generator 1/2. Minimal primes are part of the group by nature of the proof, defined technically to be prime. Primes are forming a non-abelian group under addition and multiplication. The condition to satisfy is to have an odd amount of primes under operation of addition. No matter how far into infinity we will go, the framework of vanishing of even amount of variations will ensure that all primes take the same form – aligned on 1/2.

setting the stage and examining primes not as numbers, but rather as arbitrary variations of a manifold, which vanish in pairs of even variations, we are able to show primes to form a non-abelian closed group under $2(n + 1/2)$. Final functor on the total group of primes:

$$\text{Riemann: Group} \rightarrow \text{ring}$$

All primes are forming an infinite ring on the critical line of 1/2 and only there.

End of proof.

The reasoning for choosing the numbers of "prime minimal" is due to the nature of fermions, which yield a series of two distinct elements in threefold combinations. Fermions behave according to an anti-commutation relation and vanish in pairs. There could not be a "quark" or an arbitrary variation of the manifold by itself. The series must be two and three divisible. Even amounts of opposite signs and threefold combination of elements.

Overview of reasoning

1. Deriving fermions as arbitrary variations of a Lorentz manifold
2. Arbitrary variations to vary to form threefold combinations
3. Using the fact that arbitrary variations must vanish – to derive their pairing.

Threefold combinations pairs in color.

4. Defining a prime in a context of variations – knowing that even amount of variations cancel.
5. Changing the setting from sets to rings – so we can operate addition and multiplication
6. Showing that under any multiplication – $(1/2)$ will be invariant
7. Showing that under addition – only odd amount of primes will ensure a prime, as even amounts of variations vanish. Thus, could not be a prime there.
8. Changing the settings from ring to group, from group to set, adding minimal primes, from set to group again, and group to ring.

Important note: not every odd combination of distinct higher primes will yield a prime. Same for multiplication. Certain cases will yield an odd. However, that does not diminish the beautiful result obtained, as every distinct higher prime will be formed as a combination of odd higher primes of lower magnitude. Primes are forming non-abelian group of the above form. The same reasoning allowed us to derive the awaited coupling constants series, now within the 8T framework which predicts isomorphism between primes and bosonic fields.

References

- O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)